

ENHANCED HEAVY METAL EXTRACTION FROM POST-MINING CONTAMINATED SOIL THROUGH IRON OXIDE NANOPARTICLE ADSORPTION AND SUBSEQUENT PHYTOREMEDIATION

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ABSTRACT. In the current paper, the iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) have been demonstrated to facilitate the extraction of heavy metals from post-mining contaminated soil due to their water solubility and adsorption capabilities for the target contaminants. Furthermore, IONPs were subsequently removed from the treated soil through phytoremediation and bioaccumulated in the roots and stems of legume plants. For that purpose, 20 nm IONPs coated with an organic shell of humic acid were engineered and their adsorption capacity was assessed to heavy metals as cadmium (Cd^{2+}), lead (Pb^{2+}), zinc (Zn^{2+}), manganese (Mn^{2+}), copper (Cu^{2+}), and nickel (Ni^{2+}), which are common pollutants of acid mine drainage. In the framework of phytoremediation employing legume plants, the IONPs were directly introduced into the experimental soil samples alongside compost. Subsequently, it was noted that the legume roots absorbed the nanoparticles, acting as carriers for the captured heavy metals, thus aiding in their translocation to the aboveground portions of the plants. When introduced into soil environments, humic acid-coated iron oxide nanoparticles in combination with compost may exert positive effects on rhizosphere microbial populations. This can occur through the reduction of toxic metal ion levels and the potential side reaction of degrading or transforming organic pollutants into less harmful substances. Ultimately, the heavy metals become immobilized within the plant biomass, which can subsequently be harvested and removed from the contaminated site. This process leads to soil purification and remediation. The report presented here outlines a promising avenue for practical implementation, combining organic-coated IONPs with select plants to enhance bioaccumulation of heavy metals. This approach aims to develop future cost-effective passive treatment systems for the phytoremediation of soils contaminated post-mining sites.

Key words: phytoremediation, iron oxide nanoparticles, post-mining contaminated soil, bioaccumulation

Introduction

Iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) have demonstrated their utility across a range of environmental protection endeavours, particularly in the remediation of water contaminated by heavy metals and organic pollutants (Sharma et al., 2023). Their effectiveness in adsorbing heavy metals stems from their small size, which results in a high surface area to volume ratio. Additionally, their water solubility and the potential for surface functionalization with organic ligands containing hydroxyl, carboxyl, and other groups further enhance their adsorption capabilities (Dave et al., 2014). Acid mine drainage, a common issue in mining operations, has the potential to infiltrate soil and degrade its quality by contaminating it with heavy metals, such as lead, arsenic, cadmium, and mercury, consequently disrupting the ecosystem biodiversity (Thomas et al., 2022).

Phytoremediation stands out as a leading eco-friendly method for remediating soil contaminated with heavy metals. However, it does have drawbacks, particularly concerning the phytotoxic effects of dissolved metal ions, even at low concentrations. These ions can hinder plant growth and diminish the efficiency of phytoremediation efforts. Another set of challenges and limitations of current phytoremediation methods includes the long-time frames required (often several years or even decades), the limited depth of plant roots (leaving deeper soil contaminants untreated), and the bioavailability of contaminants (non-bioavailable contaminants cannot be taken up by plants) (Ali et al., 2013; Palansooriya et al., 2020). There is also the potential for biomagnification, where contaminants enter the food chain, and biological limitations such as plant stress and poor growth in contaminated environments. Additionally, tailoring

phytoremediation to site-specific conditions can be complex and difficult (Wang and Delavar, 2024).

Nanotechnology offers promising solutions to these problems (Prasad et al., 2014). For example, nanomaterials can degrade pollutants or accelerate the transformation of contaminants, transport contaminants from deeper soil layers to the surface, improve plant uptake mechanisms, and enhance plant growth and stress tolerance (Rajput et al., 2018). Nanotechnology also facilitates the development of site-specific remediation strategies. In particular, IONPs could significantly enhance phytoremediation efforts due to their high adsorption capacity for a wide range of heavy metal ions (Ali et al., 2023). By reducing these ions to less water-soluble forms, IONPs can mitigate their toxicity, thereby contributing to more effective remediation processes (Liosis et al., 2021). Furthermore, IONPs have the capacity to be absorbed and bioaccumulated in plants via their roots, subsequently accumulating in plant tissues through several mechanisms, such as passive diffusion, active transport, and endocytosis (Gao et al., 2023).

The objective of this paper is to explore the potential of utilising iron oxide nanoparticles coated with humic acid to improve the extraction of heavy metals from post-mining contaminated soils through phytoremediation. Humic acid was chosen as a suitable capping agent due to its natural composition, which includes large polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and a diverse array of functional groups such as carbonyl, carboxyl, hydroxyl (alcoholic and phenolic), ketones, quinones, amino groups, and more (Datta et al., 2001). While the adsorption of heavy metals by humic acid-coated IONPs in wastewater treatment has been documented in the literature (Liu et al., 2008), their potential for enhancing

phytoremediation of post-mining contaminated soil has not been assessed yet. Reducing the particle size and increasing the presence of oxygen-containing organic groups on the surface of IONPs may enhance their adsorption capabilities, mobility, bioaccumulation, and overall sustainability in phytoremediation treatments.

Soybean sprouts were chosen for the phytoremediation experiments due to their rapid growth and biomass production (Hu et al., 2023), capacity to accumulate heavy metals and organic pollutants in their tissues (Sharma et al., 2016), tolerance to stress (including exposure to iron oxide nanoparticles), and a deep root system capable of penetrating soil layers to access contaminants deposited at greater depths (Prakash et al., 2023; Shahid et al., 2014; Li et al., 2019).

Experimental Procedures

Synthesis of IONPs

Magnetic iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles, approximately 20 nm in diameter, were synthesized using a bottom-up wet precipitation method and coated with humic acid. A 100 ml aqueous solution containing FeCl_3 and FeCl_2 was prepared with a stoichiometric ratio of Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} at 2:1. Specifically, 3.3 g of FeCl_3 (0.2 M) and 1.3 g of FeCl_2 (0.1 M) were dissolved in 100 ml of distilled deionized water and kept at a constant temperature of 40°C for 20 min with vigorous stirring. Additionally, 10 ml of ammonium hydroxide (25 % NH_4OH) containing 500 mg of humic acid (HA) were prepared (Ba-Abbad et al., 2022; Alomar et al., 2023). Both solutions were mixed until the pH was raised to 11, and heated under reflux at 100°C for approximately 120 minutes under Ar gas atmosphere. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature, the black residue was collected using a permanent magnet, and washed with distilled water until neutral pH of the suspension. The resulting modified nanoparticles (HA/ Fe_3O_4) as a composite adsorbent were dried for 180 min at 90°C in a vacuum oven. The chemical reaction for the synthesis of the resulted humic acid coated IONPs is proposed below (equation 1).

Equation 1. Chemical reaction for synthesis of humic acid coated Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles.

IONPs Analysis

The nanoparticles suspension's absorption was measured using UV-VIS spectroscopy (Jasco analytical spectrophotometer, model № V-570, Japan) with a 1 cm quartz cuvette. For this purpose, the nanoparticles were isolated from the reaction suspension using an external magnet and washed with distilled-deionized water. The washed nanoparticles were then resuspended in water through ultrasonication and their absorption spectra were measured (Loukanov et al., 2018b).

The stock solution was refrigerated at 4°C for two-three weeks. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were acquired using the FEI Tecnai G2 20 at 120 kV. For electron microscopic observation, a small drop ($\sim 2 \mu\text{l}$) of the washed nanoparticle suspension was placed onto a TEM copper grid coated with a carbon support film, which was pre-treated with glow discharge. The excess liquid was wicked away using filter paper. The grid was then dried in a vacuum system at ambient temperature (Williams and Carter, 1996). The FT-IR spectra of dried samples of bare Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, humic acid, and humic acid-coated Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were recorded using a Bruker TENSOR II FT-IR spectrometer equipped with a Platinum ATR (Yusoff et al., 2017). X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed on a Rigaku Smart Lab Diffractometer operating at 40 kV and 35 mA with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation (Loukanov et al., 2018a).

Batch experiments

Soil samples with a pH around neutral were obtained from culture gardening soil (originating from coco peat and perlite, No. 108, KI-19-24, G-222, Daiso Industries, Co., Ltd., Japan). These samples were initially contaminated with metal cations of cadmium (Cd^{2+}), lead (Pb^{2+}), zinc (Zn^{2+}), manganese (Mn^{2+}), nickel (Ni^{2+}), and copper (Cu^{2+}) at a concentration of 1 mg/kg to create a model sample representative of post-mining contaminated soil. For the nanoparticle treatment, 15.0 g of contaminated soil was weighed into a glass tube and mixed with an aqueous suspension that contained humic acid-coated IONPs at a 0.01 % dose (1.5 mg IONPs). The mixture was then homogenized, and 35 ml of water was added to completely fill the tube. Following nanoparticle treatment, the availability of heavy metals in the soil samples was assessed using the Toxicity Characteristic Leaching Procedure (TCLP) test (Davis, 2001). Specifically, 20 ml of sodium acetate buffer (0.1 M, pH 4.93 ± 0.05) was mixed with 1 g of soil, shaken overnight, and the concentration of metal ions in the extract was filtered and quantified by flame atomic absorption spectrometry (Sherry 2001).

Phytoremediation experiments

The soybean sprouts were purchased from Torisen Co., Ltd, Japan. The sprouts were first washed at room temperature. After washing, the sprouts were planted in pots containing either clean soil (as a control experiment) or soil contaminated with heavy metals (1 mg Me^{2+} /kg, as described in the previous experiment, to create a model post-mining contaminated soil). The sprouts were cultivated in a laboratory environment and exposed to natural sunlight. Their physiological growth was monitored for three weeks. Separately, the sprouts planted in the contaminated soil were treated with a 1.0 % aqueous suspension of HA-IONPs with compost. The water draining from the pots was collected and returned to the contaminated soil. After three weeks, the development of all plants was recorded, and the content of heavy metals and nanoparticles in the soil was quantitatively analysed. Additionally, experiments were conducted to measure the content of iron and heavy metals in the sprouts.

Quantitative analysis of the metal contents in the sprouts

The dried sprouted seeds were milled, and the resulting powder was subjected to further quantitative analysis of the iron content. A dried sample of 0.1 g of the milled powder was soaked in 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (6 M HCl) at

80°C for 30-40 minutes. The metal ion content was dissolved into the supernatant and determined by measuring the total heavy metal content through atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) using a 230ATS Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (Buck Scientific, USA). This experiment was performed with a slit of 0.15 nm and a wavelength of 248 nm. This approach allowed for the measurement of the total iron content, as well as other heavy metals that had bioaccumulated in the soybean sprouts from the polluted soil.

Results and discussions

Analysis and characterisation of the HA/Fe₃O₄ nanoadsorbent

UV-VIS absorbance spectroscopy was used to characterise the structure of both humic acid and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, as shown in Figure 1. The spectra reveal that the absorption peak of the iron oxide nanoparticles is found in the ultraviolet and visible region, with an average wavelength of 377 nm. This peak can be attributed to the intrinsic band gap absorption of the magnetic nanoparticles. The broad absorption extends into the visible range due to various electronic transitions within the nanoparticles, enabling spectrophotometric monitoring in this range. This capability is particularly important for phytoremediation experiments, as the organic compounds released by plants generally absorb only in the ultraviolet range. The UV spectra of humic acid exhibit intensive absorbance with decreasing wavelength within the range of 200 to 300 nm, reflecting the complex and varied nature of this organic compound. The absorbance in the UV range is due to the presence of multiple bonds and unshared electron pairs in the organic molecule, particularly C=C and C=O bonds from carboxyl groups, which attach to the IONPs surface, as shown in equation 1.

Figure 1. UV-Vis spectra of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (solid red line) and humic acid (thick dashed gray line)

To verify the formation of capping ligands of humic acid on the surface of the iron oxide nanoparticles, FT-IR analysis was conducted (as shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2. FT-IR spectra of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (upper, blue spectrum) and humic acid coated nanoparticles, i.e. HA/Fe₃O₄ nanoadsorbent (bottom red spectrum)

The analysis revealed the characteristic absorption peaks of HA coated Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles: 3451 cm⁻¹ attributed to -OH stretching, 1617 cm⁻¹ indicating C=O stretching vibration, 1398 cm⁻¹ assigned to -OH deformation, and 564 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the Fe-O peak. The bare Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles demonstrated a highly intensive peak at 555 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the Fe-O peak, along with weaker stretches for carboxyl groups. The phase investigation of the crystalline iron oxide nanoparticles was conducted using XRD, and the resulting diffraction pattern is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. XRD powder pattern of IONPs

The XRD pattern reveals that the product consists of magnetite (Fe₃O₄), with broad diffraction peaks indicative of a

very small crystallite size. All observed diffraction peaks correspond to the cubic structure of iron oxide, indicating a high phase purity of magnetite. The IONPs exhibited peaks at 2 Theta values of 30.0°, 35.4°, 43.2°, 53.5°, 57.0°, and 63.2°, corresponding to the (220), (331), (400), (422), (511), and (440) lattice planes, respectively. Figure 4 shows the TEM images of IONPs. For bare Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, water molecules can easily form hydrogen bonds with them due to

the presence of numerous hydroxyl groups on their surface, leading to agglomeration between nanoparticles driven by hydrogen bonds and Van der Waals forces (Figure 4A).

In contrast, the humic acid-coated IONPs are well separated from each other, likely because the organic molecules, coating the nanoparticles, hinder interactions between particles (Figure 4B).

Figure 4. Transmission electron microscopy analysis shows: (A) Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles agglomeration due to hydrogen bonds and Van der Waals forces between them, and (B) individual humic acid-coated Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, which are separated and dispersed in the micrograph. The scale bars are 20 nm for (A) and 200 nm for (B), respectively

The prepared IONPs have an average size of approximately 20 nm. Their adsorbent performance highly depends on their morphology, surface charge, and the pH of the solution. The pH of the solution significantly impacts the binding of metal ions, affecting adsorption capacity and selectivity. At pH = 2.0, the removal rates of Pb(II), Cu(II), Cd(II), and Ni(II) by HA-O/Fe₃O₄ are the lowest due to competition between hydrogen ions and metal ions for limited binding sites. As pH increases, adsorption capacity improves due to enhanced electrostatic interactions and exposure of negatively charged active centers. The highest removal rates occur at pH = 6.0, attributed to reduced hydrogen ion concentration and complex formation between metal ions and HA-O functional groups. Beyond pH 6.5, the adsorption of Pb(II) and Cu(II) decreases, potentially due to desorption of HA-O, which competes with metal ions for complexation. Cd(II) and Ni(II) adsorption increases with pH as HA-O forms weak complexes with these ions, concentrating adsorption on metal oxides rather than the HA coating. To mitigate the effects of protons and precipitation, further experiments were conducted at pH = 6.5.

Extraction of metal ions from contaminated soil using adsorption by nanoparticles, followed by phytoremediation

The presence of humic acid facilitates the uptake of heavy metals by hydrous metal oxides through various interactions.

Table 1. Percentage removal of metal cations (concentration 1 mg/kg) from aqueous solution and suspended soil by HA-coated IONPs (concentration 100 mg/kg) at pH 6.5

No	Metal ions(II)	Removal from solution, %	Removal from soil, %
1	Ni	73.8±0.5	65.7±0.2
2	Cd	92.5±0.3	78.4±0.2
3	Cu	94.6±0.3	77.5±0.1
4	Pb	97.9±0.2	89.8±0.1
5	Zn	98.7±0.2	79.3±0.1

Binding HA to IONPs promotes metal uptake due to complexation between HA and metal cations, leading to enhanced metal removal (Table 1). Literature suggests that the effectiveness of metal removal in natural systems depends on the presence of organic matter in water (Gu et al., 1994). After three weeks of phytoremediation of the contaminated soil using soybean sprouts, the plants were extracted, washed, dried, and milled. The inorganic metal content in the dried residue was then analysed quantitatively. The accumulated iron content was approximately 7.2 % higher than the average iron content observed in the control experiment, suggesting that some HA-IONPs were taken up by the plants. The bioaccumulated heavy metal content is presented in Table 2,

with lead having the highest accumulation, constituting over 6 % of the total metal content.

Table 2. Total inorganic metal content ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{ g dry matter}$) in soybean sprouts germinated in soil with HA-IONPs at a concentration of 100 mg/kg, heavy metals at 1 mg/kg, and a pH around neutral

Ions (II)	Me(II) content ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{ g d.m.}$)	Control exp. ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{ g d.m.}$)	Removal from soil, %
Ni	95.72 \pm 0.55	48 \pm 0.5	4.8 \pm 0.5
Cd	57.35 \pm 0.45	1.1 \pm 0.2	5.6 \pm 0.3
Cu	453.70 \pm 0.43	398 \pm 0.6	5.6 \pm 0.5
Pb	74.86 \pm 0.38	11.2 \pm 0.3	6.4 \pm 0.2
Zn	1935.2 \pm 1.1	1879 \pm 0.8	5.7 \pm 0.2

In our experiments, gardening soil sourced from coco peat and perlite was used. It is important to note that these materials can vary in mineral content depending on their geological origin. Of particular interest are two observations: first, the higher concentrations of zinc and copper, both crucial for plant growth and development; and second, the relatively constant ratio (in μg per unit mass) between these metals in the plant in both control and phytoremediation experiment. Our findings indicate very low concentrations of heavy metals such as cadmium and lead, suggesting that this soil is suitable for gardening and bioremediation applications, respectively. Experimental data demonstrate effective removal of metal ions, particularly cadmium and lead, which exhibit significant bioaccumulation in plants compared to their natural levels. This underscores the efficiency of the proposed method.

The mechanism of nanoparticle accumulation and storage in plants is actively under investigation. Current data indicate that plants primarily absorb nanoparticles through their roots. In soil, nanoparticles can interact with the rhizosphere and organic matter, leading to complex reactions that influence their transformation. Subsequently, nanoparticles may accumulate in plant roots and distribute throughout various plant tissues. It has been found that adding compost to the growing scheme positively affects metal toxicity reduction in the rhizosphere and enhances phytoremediation. As a rich source of organic matter, compost enhances microbial activity, stimulates the growth and activity of beneficial microorganisms (Loukanov et al., 2019), and alters the surface properties and mobility of nanoparticles (Belal et al., 2016), thereby improving their uptake by plants. In the control experiment (phytoremediation without HA-IONPs and organic matter), inorganic metals, particularly cadmium, initially induce various phytotoxic effects, such as root damage and decreased microbial activity. However, ongoing research investigations are still underway.

Conclusion

The study showcases the use of iron oxide nanoparticles coated with humic acid as an environmentally friendly nano-adsorbent for toxic metals in soil. These nanoparticles, once loaded with toxic metals, can be bioaccumulated by soybean sprouts, thereby enhancing the phytoremediation of

contaminated soil. Consequently, the application of HA-coated iron oxide nanoparticles in phytoremediation presents a promising and versatile strategy for remediating post-mining soil contaminated with heavy metals. Future research should prioritise gaining a deeper understanding of plant-nanoparticle interactions to optimise experimental systems and enhance phytoremediation efficiency. Long-term trials are essential to evaluate the effectiveness and sustainability of HA-coated iron oxide nanoparticles in real-world scenarios. Such trials would offer insights into their performance across diverse environmental conditions and over extended durations.

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References

- Ali, H., Khan, E. & Sajad, M. A. (2013). Phytoremediation of heavy metals - concepts and applications. *Chemosphere*, 91, 869–881. DOI: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.01.075
- Ali, Q., Zia, M. A., Kamran, M., Shabaan, M., Zulfikar, U., Ahmad, M., Iqbal, R. & Maqsood, M. F. (2023). Nanoremediation for heavy metal contamination: A review. *Hybrid Advances*, 4, 100091. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hybadv.2023.100091>
- Alomar, T., Qiblawey, H., Almomani, F., Al-Raoush, R. I., Han, D. S. & Ahmad N. M. (2023). Recent advances on humic acid removal from wastewater using adsorption process. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, 53, 103679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2023.103679>
- Ba-Abbad, M. M., Benamour, A., Ewis, D., Mohammad, A. W. & Mahmoudi, E. (2022). Synthesis of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with different shapes through a co-precipitation method and their application. *JOM*, 74, 3531–3539. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-022-05380-3>
- Belal, E. S. & El-Ramady, H. (2016). Nanoparticles in Water, Soils and Agriculture. In S. Ranjan, N. Dasgupta, & E. Lichtfouse (Eds) *Nanoscience in Food and Agriculture 2. Sustainable Agriculture Reviews*, vol 21. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-39306-3_10
- Datta, A., Sanya, I S. & Saha, S. (2001). A study on natural and synthetic humic acids and their complexing ability towards cadmium. *Plant and Soil*, 235, 115–125. DOI: 10.1023/A:1011842019753
- Dave, P. & Chopda, L. (2014). Application of iron oxide nanomaterials for the removal of heavy metals. *Journal of Nanotechnology*, Article 398569. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/398569>
- Gao, M., Chang, J., Wang, Z., Zhang, H. & Wang, T. (2023). Advances in transport and toxicity of nanoparticles in plants. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 21, Article 75. doi: 10.1186/s12951-023-01830-5
- Gu, B., Shmitt, J., Chen, Z., Liang, L. & McCarthy J. (1994). Adsorption and desorption of natural organic matter on iron oxide: mechanisms and models. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 28, 38–46. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es00050a007>
- Hu, Z., Lei, Y., Zhang, J., Tong, W., Zhang, Y. & Du, L. (2023). Physiological characterization, antioxidant potential, and bacterial survival of soybean sprouts subjected to pre- and post-harvest low intensity ultrasound and exogenous ascorbic acid application. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 198, 112258.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2023.112258>
- Li, Z., Deblon, J., Zu, Y., Colinet, G., Li, B. & He, Y. (2019). Geochemical Baseline Values Determination and Evaluation of Heavy Metal Contamination in Soils of Lanping Mining Valley (Yunnan Province, China). *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health.*, 16(23), 4686. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16234686>
- Liosis, C., Papadopoulou, A., Karvelas, E., Karakasidis, T., Sarris, I. (2021). Heavy metal adsorption using magnetic nanoparticles for water purification: a critical review. *Materials (Basel)*, 14, Article 7500. doi: 10.3390/ma14247500
- Liu, J., Zhao, Z. & Jiang, G. (2008). Coating Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles with humic acid for high efficient removal of heavy metals in water. *Environmental Science & Technology* 42, 18, 6949–6954. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es800924c>
- Loukanov, A., Angelov, A., Takahashi, Y., Nikolov, I., Nakabayashi, S. (2019). Carbon nanodots chelated with metal ions as efficient electrocatalysts for enhancing performance of microbial fuel cell based on sulfate reducing bacteria. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 574, 52–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2019.04.067>
- Loukanov, A., Basnakian, A., Kawamura, R., Udono, H., Filipov, C., Savenska, A., Fite, T. & Nakabayashi, S. (2018a). Light-powered nanoconverters cytotoxic to breast cancer cells. *ACS Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 122 (14), 7916–7924. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.7b11779>
- Loukanov, A., Mladenova, P., Udono, H., Miskolc, Z., Angelov, A., Biczok, L. & Nakabayashi, S. (2018b). Sulfur doped fluorescent carbon dots as nanosensors for rapid and sensitive monitoring of calcium in hard water. *Journal of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy*, 53, 473–479. https://journal.uctm.edu/node/j2018-3/9_18-21_p_473-479_new.pdf
- Palansooriya, K. N., Shaheen, S. M., Chen, S. S., Tsang, D. C. W., Hashimoto, Y., Hou, D., Bolan, N. S., Rinklebe, J. & Ok, Y. S. (2020). Soil amendments for immobilization of potentially toxic elements in contaminated soils: A critical review. *Environment International*, 134, 105046. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.105046>
- Prakash, P. & Chandran S. S. (2023). Nano-phytoremediation of heavy metals from soil: a critical review. *Pollutants*, 3(3), 360–380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pollutants3030025>
- Prasad, R., Kumar, V. & Prasad K. S. (2014). Nanotechnology in sustainable agriculture: present concerns and future aspects. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 13(6), 705–713. DOI: 10.5897/AJBX2013.13554
- Rajput, V. D., Minkina, T., Behal, A., Sushkova, S. N., Mandzhieva, S., Singh, R., Gorovtsov, A., Tsitsuashvili, V.S., Purvis, W.O., Ghazaryan, A. & Movsesyan, H. S. Ghazaryan, K. A. (2018). Effects of zinc-oxide nanoparticles on soil, plants, animals and soil organisms: A review. *Environmental Nanotechnology, Monitoring & Management*, 9, 76–84. DOI: 10.1016/j.enmm.2017.12.006
- Shahid, M., Pinelli, E., Pourrut, B., Silvestre, J. & Dumat, C. (2011). Lead-induced genotoxicity to *Vicia faba* L. roots in relation with metal cell uptake and initial speciation. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 74, 78–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2010.08.037>
- Sharma, R., Garg, R., Bali, M., Eddy, N. (2023). Potential applications of green-synthesized iron oxide NPs for environmental remediation. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 195, Article 1397. doi: 10.1007/s10661-023-12035-6
- Sharma, S. S., Dietz, K. J. & Mimura, T. (2016). Vacuolar compartmentalization as indispensable component of heavy metal detoxification in plants. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 39(5), 1112–1126. DOI: 10.1111/pce.12706
- Sherry, D. (2001). *Regulated Metals: The Rule of 20*. Pollution Prevention Institute, Kansas State University. <https://p2infohouse.org/ref/48/47822.pdf>
- Thomas, G., Sheridan, C. & Holm, P. (2022). A critical review of phytoremediation for acid mine drainage-impacted environments. *Science of The Total Environment*, 811, Article 152230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152230>
- Wang, J. & Delavar, M. A. (2024). Modelling phytoremediation: Concepts, methods, challenges and perspectives. *Soil & Environmental Health*, 2(1), 100062. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seh.2024.100062>
- Williams, D. B. & Carter, C. B. (1996). *Transmission Electron Microscopy: A Textbook for Materials Science*. Springer. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-0-387-76501-3>
- Yusoff, A. H. M., Salimi, M. N. & Jamlos, M. F. (2017). Synthesis and characterization of biocompatible Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles at different pH. *AIP Conf. Proc.*, 1835, 020010. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4981832>